

Sustainable Development and Regional Planning Strategies (A Case Study of Azerbaijan's Liberated Territories)

Narmin Ahmadova

Global Management And Politics Master Degree ADA - LUISS (Italy)

Email: ahmadovanarmin@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigates in which ways Azerbaijani government's reconstruction plans of Nagorno-Karabakh in post-war era aligns with regional development of Sustainable Development Goals. Evaluating the adoption of "green" and "smart" solutions, the thesis puts an emphasis on the progress of energy transition and infrastructure management. Findings highlight the necessity of including more community participation, monitoring and SDG alignment. In comparison with the other post-conflict cases, the study provides policy recommendations in order to improve the alignment of reconstruction plans in terms of environmental sustainability, inclusivity, and robust regional development planning.

Keywords: Post-conflict Reconstruction, Sustainability, Spatial planning, Resilient Urban Development, Nagorno-Karabakh, Smart Cities

1. Introduction

Background

After decades of conflict and occupation, Azerbaijan has started to implement one of the most comprehensive post-conflict reconstruction plans in liberated territories. A new era of national development has been marked by the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh war as reconstruction of infrastructure, resettlement of people, and integration of sustainability into regional planning principles have become the priorities.

Problem Statement

In spite of comprehensive reconstruction plans and sustainability strategies in the liberated lands, great amount of difficulties prevail in operationalizing policy goals effectively.

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

- Deliver an in-depth analysis of Azerbaijan's post-conflict reconstruction strategies
- Apply comparative analysis, stakeholder observations and gap evaluations to assess the alignment of process with the SDGs
- Recommend the promotion of inclusivity and robust planning in unstable environments

Scientific Novelty

The novelty lays in providing in-depth evaluation of Azerbaijan's ways of handling post-conflict reconstructions criteria by the lenses of sustainable planning, suggesting a model suitable for other regions with the same conditions.

2. Methodology and Data

Study Area

A qualitative case study model is used to figure out to which extent Azerbaijan's reconstruction plans fits in sustainable development goals.

Data Collection

- **Multi-method qualitative data collection: document analysis**

1. The "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-economic Development"

2. State Committee for Urban Planning and Architecture of Azerbaijan's statements and Reports
3. Project summaries and national reports from UNDP Azerbaijan covering the green energy and smart village initiatives in Aghdam, Susha, and Fuzuli
4. Azerbaijan's SDG Voluntary National Reviews
5. Whenever applicable development and planning records from global organizations

- **Semi-structured interviews**

1. Officials of the appropriate ministries (e.g., Urban Planning Committee, Ministry of Economy)
2. Professionals from international development institutions such as the UNDP and EU Delegation to Azerbaijan)
3. Independent researchers and scholars with specialization in regional planning or post-conflict reconstruction
4. Representatives of civil society who are familiar with the needs of the local community

4. Estimation Results

Some obstacles to achieve a successful reconstruction plan occurred as a result of the study:

- Insufficient institutional coordination and lack of administrative capacity
- Logistical and structural problems
- Inadequate monitoring and assessment
- Insufficient waste management and recycling facilities

5. Conclusion

This study illustrates that long-term regional change is highly impacted by the implementation of Azerbaijan's post-conflict reconstruction program. In spite of integrated steps, sustainable urban planning is not achieved fully due to some barriers. Policy-makers need to prioritize more inclusive, flexible, and sustainable planning in the long-run.

6. References (APA 7)

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